

FACT-CENTERED ORGANIZATION OF DIGITAL INFORMATION FLOW IN MULTI-AGENT SYSTEMS AND INCREMENTAL MAINTENANCE OF THE REPOSITORY

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Abstract. *This paper proposes a fact-centric method for organizing digital information streams and incrementally maintaining a fact repository in multi-agent systems. Formal models of an agent, a digital stream record, a fact, and a local repository state are presented. The processes of inserting new records and normalized facts into the repository, linking them to existing facts, merging semantically similar facts, updating attributes, and moving facts to a terminal state are described using the Insert, Link, Merge, Update, and Close operators. The proposed approach reduces semantic redundancy, preserves evidence-based relations, and ensures consistent fact life-cycle management. Experimental results show that processing 20,000 raw records produced 6,319 final facts and reduced the data volume by 68.41%. The results confirm that the method is effective for fact-centric analysis of digital streams and stable repository maintenance in a multi-agent environment.*

Keywords: *multi-agent system, digital information stream, fact-centric approach, fact repository, incremental maintenance, Insert, Link, Merge, Update, Close, semantic relation.*

Introduction. It is widely acknowledged that in multi-agent systems, digital information streams are often generated by multiple independent or semi-independent sources. Because electronic applications, service logs, video surveillance events, sensor records, and other digital streams are syntactically, semantically, and structurally distinct, processing them within a unified analytical framework is a complex scientific and practical task. In modern digital control environments, there is a growing need to consider stream data not as a simple set of records, but as a system of meaningful units supporting monitoring, auditing, and management decision-making [1-5].

Significant scientific advances have been made worldwide in the fields of multi-agent system theory, distributed problem solving, inter-agent coordination, and information flow processing. Recent research has shown that the multi-agent approach is used in such tasks as managing complex engineering environments, automatically validating and correcting data from web sources, and generating annotations for time series in various fields. This confirms the growing importance, not only of theoretical but also of practical approaches to digital data processing based on inter-agent collaboration [1-5, 9-11].

However, existing studies offer solutions primarily focused on specific application areas, while the issue of reorganizing the flow of digital information from various sources in a multi-agent environment based on a unified fact model, consistently maintaining facts extracted from it in a repository, and enriching them with subsequent records has not been sufficiently comprehensively addressed. Separating facts alone is insufficient; they must be linked, merged, updated, or converted to a complete state with subsequent records. Therefore, it is important to

consider the local state of the repository as a dynamic structure and develop a method for its incremental maintenance [5, 8, 12].

The goal of this article is to develop a method for fact-centered organization of digital information flow in multi-agent systems and incremental maintenance of a fact repository. To achieve this goal, the formal foundations of agents, streaming records, facts, and local repository state are briefly described. A model for dynamic repository state change is presented. An incremental maintenance mechanism based on Insert, Link, Merge, Update, and Close operators is described, and its practical effectiveness is illustrated through prototype experiments.

The formal model of a fact-centered organization. In multi-agent systems, a digital information flow is a sequence of records arriving from different sources. In such an environment, individual agents are viewed as functional entities that receive data, perform initial processing, and form a local knowledge state [1, 2, 5]. Therefore, it is advisable to interpret the flow not as a simple set of records, but as an information environment that should be divided into meaningful units.

A set of agents

$$A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\},$$

where a_i is the i -agent, m is the number of agents in the system. The elementary unit of a digital stream is a record, which is expressed as:

$$x = \langle \mu, v, \tau, \rho, \eta \rangle,$$

where μ is the source identifier, v is the raw content of the record, τ is the timestamp, ρ is the set of attributes, and η is the set of evidential or application components.

In a fact-centered approach, the object of analysis is not the record itself, but a fact that can be extracted from it. A fact is defined as:

$$f = \langle k, s, r, h, t, d, w \rangle,$$

where k is the unique key of the fact, s is the source agent or system, r is the referent, h is the semantics of the event, t is the timestamp, d is the evidential description, and w is the reliability score [8].

This model allows us to consider records from different sources, but representing the same or related event, in a single semantic space.

A local set of facts for each agent

$$F_i = \{f_{i1}, f_{i2}, \dots, f_{in_i}\}$$

However, fact-centric organization is not limited to storing facts. For this purpose, the agent's local repository state

$$\Lambda_i = \langle F_i, L_i, U_i \rangle$$

where F_i is the set of local facts, L_i is the relationships between facts, and U_i is the history of updates. When a new record arrives, the repository state changes as $\Lambda_i^{(n)} \rightarrow \Lambda_i^{(n+1)}$.

It is important to note that the formal model of fact-centered organization represents the relationships between agents, records, facts, and local repository in a unified way. This model serves as the theoretical basis for the incremental repository maintenance method discussed in the next section.

Incremental fact repository maintenance model. The practical value of fact-centered analysis in multi-agent systems is not determined solely by the separation of facts. The main problem is that the digital stream is constantly updated, and each new record or new evidentiary component can change the existing knowledge state. Therefore, the local repository should not be considered a static repository, but a dynamic environment that is enriched over time. From this

point of view, the incremental repository maintenance model is one of the central mechanisms of fact-centered organization [9].

Local repository state

$$\Lambda_i^{(n)} = \langle F_i^{(n)}, L_i^{(n)}, U_i^{(n)} \rangle$$

where $F_i^{(n)}$ is the set of local facts at step n , $L_i^{(n)}$ - is the set of links between facts, and $U_i^{(n)}$ - is the update history. Now, at step $n+1$ - let the agent receive a new normalized fact f_{new} . In this case, updating the repository state is represented by the following general transition operator:

$$\psi_i : (\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}) \rightarrow \Lambda_i^{(n+1)}$$

The task of this operator is to compare the newly arrived fact with the existing repository state semantically and evidence-wise, identify facts that match it, and determine what type of change will occur in the repository [8].

In the first stage of incremental processing, a set of suitable candidates for the new fact in the repository is formed:

$$C_i(f_{new}) = \{ f \in F_i^{(n)} \mid Sim(f, f_{new}) \geq \theta \}$$

where $Sim(\cdot, \cdot)$ - is the similarity function, and θ is the minimum matching threshold. The meaning of this stage is that instead of completely comparing all facts in the repository, only those facts that are sufficiently close in terms of referent, event type, temporal proximity, or evidential components are extracted. As a result, it is determined with which existing unit in the repository the new fact can be associated or combined.

If $C_i(f_{new}) = \emptyset$ that is, no suitable candidate for the new fact is found, then f_{new} is entered into the repository as a new independent fact. This indicates the appearance of a new event or previously unobserved object. On the contrary, if the candidate set is not empty, then the place of the new fact in the repository is determined based on the degree of semantic similarity, evidential proximity, and temporal consistency. It is at this stage that the main decision points for incrementally maintaining the repository arise.

We divide the general logic for updating the repository state into four main cases.

In the first case, a new fact is very similar in content to an existing fact and essentially represents a new evidential representation of that fact. In this case, the new fact is not introduced as a separate entity, but is merged with an existing fact. This reduces repository redundancy, and different records about the same event are combined into a single fact.

In the second case, the new fact is not completely identical to an existing fact, but is semantically or evidentially related to it. For example, records related to the same object but representing different stages of an event create this situation. In this case, the facts are not merged, but a relationship is established between them. This approach preserves the history of facts and the internal structure of events.

In the third case, the new fact enriches the state or evidential content of an existing fact. For example, an additional timestamp, a new status, additional explanation, or evidence can be added to a previously extracted fact. In this case, the fact in the repository is updated rather than rewritten. This provides historical and semantic enrichment for the fact.

In the fourth situation, a newly received record or fact indicates the final state of an existing fact. For example, the closure of an open incident, the resolution of a complaint, or the resolution of a technical issue is recorded. In this case, the fact is moved to its final state, and its lifecycle in the repository is considered complete.

These situations can be generally expressed as follows:

$$\Lambda_i^{(n+1)} = \begin{cases} \text{Insert}(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}), C_i(f_{new}) = \emptyset, \\ \text{Merge}(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}, f^*), \exists f^* \in C_i(f_{new}) \text{ and a strong match } \exists, \\ \text{Link}(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}, f^*), \exists f^* \in C_i(f_{new}) \text{ va bog'liqlik } \exists, \\ \text{Update}(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}, f^*), \exists f^* \in C_i(f_{new}) \text{ and if there is evidence of enrichment,} \\ \text{Close}(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f^*), f^* \text{ if a terminal condition is detected for.} \end{cases}$$

Here f^* - is the most relevant or preferred candidate fact in the repository. This expression provides a general conceptual model of repository updating; the formal description of specific operators is given in the next section.

The incremental maintenance model must satisfy three practical requirements at the same time. First, it must not allow the repository to grow indefinitely with redundant items. Second, it must not lose useful evidence from new entries, i.e., it must preserve the richness of the knowledge content. Third, it must ensure the consistent development of the history of facts over time. Therefore, the incremental maintenance model is considered a dynamic mechanism based on semantic decision-making, in contrast to the simple “append-only” repository approach.

From a practical point of view, the advantage of this model is that it constantly updates the fact repository in a multi-agent environment, while ensuring the compactness and consistency of the overall fact space. As the flow of new records increases, the number of knowledge units in the repository does not increase proportionally to the number of raw records; on the contrary, close records are combined, related cases are maintained in a related manner, and evidence is aggregated in a way that enriches a single semantic core. This is an important condition for improving the quality of subsequent search, monitoring, and analytical conclusions.

The incremental maintenance model of a fact repository is considered as a dynamic transition mechanism that connects a new fact with an existing knowledge state. This model allows us to formally represent the state of the repository at each new step, determine the place of incoming records in the repository, and ensure semantically consistent updating.

Incremental operators and consistency invariants. This section describes the incremental operators that form the practical core of this transition, as well as the invariants that ensure the consistency of the repository. In our opinion, the efficient maintenance of a fact repository in a multi-agent environment is determined not only by the addition of new facts, but also by a set of specific operators that control semantic proximity, evidence enrichment, and state exchange between them [8].

When a new normalized fact f_{new} arrives in the repository, a set of local state update operators is used

$$\Omega = \{\text{Insert}, \text{Link}, \text{Merge}, \text{Update}, \text{Close}\}$$

Each operator introduces a certain type of change to the repository state, and together they $\Lambda_i^{(n+1)} = \omega(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}), \omega \in \Omega$ creates a general transition in the form of.

Insert operator. If no semantically suitable candidate for a new fact is found in the repository, then the new fact is inserted as an independent unit:

$$\text{Insert}(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}) \Rightarrow F_i^{(n+1)} = F_i^{(n)} \cup \{f_{new}\}.$$

This operator represents a new object, a new event, or a previously unrecorded situation. The main task of the insert operator is to insert a new knowledge unit into the repository without losing it.

Link operator. If the new fact is not exactly the same as the existing fact, but they are different stages of the same object, traces from different sources, or semantically related manifestations, a connection is established between them:

$$Link(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}, f^*) \Rightarrow L_i^{(n+1)} = L_i^{(n)} \cup \{(f_{new}, f^*, \ell)\},$$

where ℓ is the type of connection. This operator does not merge facts, but preserves the relationship between them. This is especially important for viewing traces of an event from different observation channels together.

Merge operator. If a new fact and an existing fact have a strong semantic match, that is, they are repeated or very close expressions of the same event, they are merged into a single fact:

$$Merge(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}, f) \Rightarrow f^{\oplus} = f_{new} \sqcup f^*,$$

where \sqcup is the attribute consolidation operator. The Merge operator serves to reduce redundancy in the repository, to collect fragmented records of the same event into a single semantic core, and to simplify further analysis.

Update operator. If a new fact enriches the content of an existing fact, but does not completely replace it, then the existing fact is updated:

$$Update(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f_{new}, f^*) \Rightarrow f^{\uparrow} = \varphi(f^*, f_{new}),$$

$$F_i^{(n+1)} = (F_i^{(n)} \setminus \{f^*\}) \cup \{f^{\uparrow}\}.$$

Here φ - is an evidence or attribute enrichment function. For example, a new timestamp, additional status, new evidence, or comment can be added to an existing fact. The Update operator provides evolutionary enrichment of facts in the repository.

Close operator. If a final state is determined for a fact, it is transferred to a terminal state:

$$Close(\Lambda_i^{(n)}, f^*) \Rightarrow status(f^*) = closed.$$

This operator records the resolution of a request, the elimination of a technical failure, or the completion of an event. The Close operator controls the life cycle of facts in the repository.

For the above operators to work effectively, a number of consistency invariants must be maintained in the state of the repository.

Invariant 1 (uniformity). The number of duplicate active facts with the same semantic content in the repository should be minimal. This can be expressed as follows:

$$\forall f_p, f_q \in F_i^{(n)},$$

$$(Sim(f_p, f_q) \geq \theta_m \wedge status(f_p) \neq closed \wedge status(f_q) \neq closed) \Rightarrow p = q.$$

This invariant represents the theoretical basis of the Merge operator and limits the appearance of redundant semantic duplicates in the active repository.

Invariant 2. (Evidence monotonicity) When a fact is updated or merged, its evidence base should not decrease: $D(f^{(n+1)}) \supseteq D(f^{(n)})$, where $D(f)$ - is the set of evidence components of the fact. This invariant guarantees that information is not lost when the Update and Merge operators are used.

Invariant 3 (time consistency). The time attributes of a fact should not violate the natural time order of the event. If t_{new} is a new evidential time, then the time description of the updated fact is defined as $t^{(n+1)} = \psi(t^{(n)}, t_{new})$, where ψ denotes a consistent aggregation of time in minimum, maximum, or interval form. As a result, the development of the fact history over time is preserved.

Invariant 4 (terminal state stability). If a fact has passed into the closed state, then subsequent new entries should not reactivate this fact, but should be treated as a new fact or a connected state, if necessary:

$$\text{status}(f^*) = \text{closed} \Rightarrow \neg \text{reopen}(f^*)$$

or reactivation must be controlled by a separate rule. This invariant preserves the consistency of completed states in the repository.

Based on these invariants, the following general sequence of incremental maintenance operator applications is formed: first, suitable candidates for a new fact are identified; then, the Merge operation is used if there is a strong match, the Link operation if the relationship is dominant, the Update operation if attribute enrichment occurs, the Close operation if the final state is determined, and the Insert operation if no suitable candidate exists. Thus, operator selection is viewed as a decision-making process dependent on semantic proximity, evidence enrichment, and state description.

The proposed operator system achieves three main effects in the repository. First, it limits the linear growth of the number of source records relative to the number of facts in the repository. Second, it enables the unification of evidence dispersed across different records into a unified core of facts. Third, it creates a structurally stable knowledge base for monitoring and subsequent retrieval stages, managing the fact lifecycle.

It is worth mentioning that incremental maintenance mechanism based on the Insert, Link, Merge, Update, and Close operators enables the fact repository to be maintained as a dynamic, consistent, and semantically rich environment. This set of operators elevates the flow of digital information in multi-agent systems to a level of fact-oriented knowledge management, as opposed to simple archiving.

Experimental and test results and analysis. For evaluating the practical effectiveness of the proposed fact-oriented organization and incremental repository maintenance method, experimental and test work was conducted using the FaktRepo-Prototype and FaktAnalytika-Prototype software tools. Specifically, NYC 311 service requests [13] were chosen to represent the flow of text queries, and Blue Gene/L supercomputer logs [14] were chosen to represent the flow of service logs. This choice allowed us to test the proposed model's performance across digital flows of varying nature within a single experimental setup.

It should be pointed out that this article focuses on the repository maintenance mechanism, the experiment focused on how new incoming records interact with facts in the repository. That is, after normalizing the stream records, we observe their insertion into the local repository as a new fact, linking to an existing fact, merging with a fact of similar content, enriching an existing fact, or transitioning to a final state. Thus, the effectiveness of the Insert, Link, Merge, Update, and Close operators was experimentally assessed in a real stream.

The experiment processed 20,000 raw records from the open call stream, ultimately generating 6,319 facts in the repository. In this case, the Insert statement was used 20,000 times, the Link statement 19,544 times, the Merge statement 13,681 times, and the Close statement 6,319 times. No special uses of the Update statement were observed in this experimental scenario. As a result, the data volume was reduced by 68.41%. These results demonstrate that repository maintenance is not simply a sequential addition of records, but an active mechanism based on the reorganization and consolidation of their contents.

Table 1 shows that instead of storing each record in the source stream as a separate, independent unit, the proposed approach combines them into a system of facts linked by semantic proximity, timestamp, object, and event type.

Table 1. Experimental results for incremental maintenance of a fact-oriented repository.

Indicator	Value
Number of raw stream records	20000
The number of final facts in the repository	6319
Number of consolidated records, Merge	13681
Number of evidence linking operations, Link	19544
Number of insert operations	20000
Number of update operations	0
Number of Close operations	6319
Shortening, %	68,41

Analyzing the obtained results from a content perspective, we see that the Insert operator initially works for all incoming records. However, the fact that the number of facts in the final repository state is 6,319 instead of 20,000 indicates the high efficiency of the Merge and Link operators. In particular, the Merge result of 13,681 indicates that a large number of records in the stream are similar in content or are duplicate instances of the same event. Thus, the proposed mechanism effectively reduced semantic duplication in the repository and combined fragmented traces of a single event into a single fact.

The Link result of 19,544 demonstrates another important advantage of the repository support mechanism. That is, new records are not only merged but also supported by facts and semantically linked to existing facts. This is important for maintaining a consistent fact history, preserving the stages of event development, and subsequent monitoring. Thus, Merge ensured the compactness of the repository, while Link preserved its internal content coherence.

The result Close = 6319 shows that the number of facts transferred to the final state in the repository matches the number of final facts. This indicates that the principle of final state stability is indeed valid in the incremental maintenance model. In other words, each final fact generated in the experimental process completed its life cycle at a specific point and is written to the repository as a consistently complete unit.

These results demonstrate three main practical advantages of the proposed model. First, the number of source records is dramatically reduced, resulting in a more compact and manageable fact space in the repository. Second, the level of fact interpretability is increased by preserving fact-based relationships. Third, by consistently managing the fact lifecycle from insertion to closure, a high-quality knowledge base was created for subsequent retrieval and monitoring processes. In this regard, the proposed incremental maintenance model demonstrates significant superiority over a simple approach based solely on data addition.

Experimental results confirmed the practical effectiveness of fact-centered organization of digital information flows and incremental data warehouse maintenance in multi-agent systems. Results obtained on an open data flow demonstrated the feasibility of reducing redundancy in the data warehouse, maintaining relationships, consistently managing final states, and generating a finite fact space. This situation serves as a scientific and practical basis for applying the proposed approach in real-world multi-agent monitoring and control systems.

Conclusion. This study proposes a method for fact-centered organization of digital information flows and incremental data warehouse maintenance in multi-agent systems. The work is based on a formal model of an agent, a digital flow record, a fact, and the local state of the data warehouse, as well as an approach to transferring flow elements from the level of source records to the level of meaningful fact-event units. A model representing dynamic changes in the repository state is also presented, along with an incremental maintenance mechanism based on the Insert, Link, Merge, Update, and Close operators.

The main advantage of the proposed approach is that it goes beyond simply adding new incoming records, sequentially reorganizing them into repositories based on semantic proximity, evidence enrichment, and state changes. This ensures compactness of the actual space, preservation of links between evidence, and stable maintenance of final states. This enables information flow management at the knowledge unit level in multi-agent monitoring and control environments.

Figure 1. Comparative diagram of the number of raw records and final facts.

The experimental results confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed method. In particular, 6319 final facts were generated as a result of processing 20,000 raw records, and the data volume was reduced by 68.41% due to the active use of Merge, Link and Close operators. This shows that the incremental model of repository management is effective in transforming the flow of raw records into a semantically ordered and usable space of facts for further analysis.

It is becoming increasingly clear that the proposed method of fact-centered organization and incremental repository management creates the necessary methodological basis for intelligent management of digital information flows in multi-agent systems and serves as a scientific foundation for solving the problems of indexing, selective inter-agent search and federated analytics at the next stages.

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